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SYSTEM ANALYSIS OF THE ONTOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE NATURE OF
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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to current issues of socio-political development - system analysis of the ontological foundations of the nature of freedom as a fundamental value. The state should control the freedom of human rights not by means of violence and coercion, but by economic mechanism and strict observance of human rights. The state must guarantee the observance of human rights, recognizing that the value of the human being is higher than any value of the nation, class, group of people, etc.

Key words: freedom, existentialism, right, value, freedom of belief, responsibility, choice.

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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕННОСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена актуальным вопросам общественно-политического развития - системному анализу онтологических основ природы свободы как фундаментальной ценности. Государство должно контролировать свободу прав человека не посредством насилия и принуждения, а посредством экономического механизма и строгого соблюдения прав человека. Государство должно гарантировать соблюдение прав человека, признавая, что ценность человека выше любой ценности нации, класса, группы людей и т. д.

Ключевые слова: свобода, экзистенциализм, право, ценность, свобода убеждений, ответственность, выбор.

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**FUNDAMENTAL QADRIYAT SIFATIDAGI ERKINLIK TABIATINING ONTOLOGIK
ASOSLARINI TIZIMLI TAXLILI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqola ijtimoiy-siyosiy rivojlanishning dolzarb masalalariga - erkinlik mohiyatining ontologik asoslarini fundamental qadriyat sifatida tizimli tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Davlat inson huquqlari erkinligini zo'ravonlik va majburlash yo'li bilan emas, balki iqtisodiy mexanizm va inson huquqlariga qat'iy rioya qilish orqali nazorat qilishi kerak. Davlat insonning qadr-qimmatini millat, tabaqa, odamlar guruhi va boshqalarning har qanday qadriyatidan yuqori ekanligini tan olgan holda, inson huquqlariga rioya etilishini kafolatlashi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: erkinlik, ekzistensializm, huquq, qadriyat, e'tiqod erkinligi, mas'uliyat, tanlov.

INTRODUCTION. The world surrounding a person is represented by many relationships between objects, including the concepts of freedom and arbitrariness. Thinkers of different times and cultures have addressed and continue to address the problem of freedom. The concept of freedom is mostly used in the analysis of the voluntary behavior of a person, the legal aspects of his existence, and in the subjective description of the state of society. Social existence and legal issues are directly confirmed in each country by its own laws and bylaws. A clear example is that in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the draft of the new Constitution was considered and approved by the people. A person, reflecting the direction vectors of the activity of the object of existence, relates to the concept of freedom in the form of "being free from something" or "being free for something". The understanding of freedom is ontological and axiological.

LITERATURE REVIEW.

Despite the fact that thinkers have been dealing with the problem of freedom from ancient times to the present, the place of freedom in the system of general relationships of existence, the nature of these relationships has not yet been determined. Various aspects of the essence and nature of freedom Plato [1], Aristotle [2], A. Augustine [3], A. Canterbury, B. Spinoza, I. Kant, G. Hegel, B.C. Solov'ev, H.A. Considered by such philosophers as Berdyaev, M. Heidegger, A. Camus.

In particular, in ancient times, freedom was considered to be the highest blessing and virtue. Freedom is explained as the right of the gods, far from the fleeting desires of this world. However, man has always been in the depths of passions, pleasures, wars and conflicts, which have led him away from the path of goodness and goodness. The views of the philosophers of that time about freedom changed due to the emergence of views on democracy in antiquity and the continuation of slavery at the same time. For example, Aristotle very clearly distinguished a free man from a slave: "Nature is structured in such a way that the physical structure of free people differs from the physical structure of a part of society such as slaves: the body of slaves is strong and has to do the necessary hard work, on the contrary, free people though incapable of doing such things, men fit for political life, but in many cases free men, are free not by reason of their physical constitution, but by the constitution of their minds. Although it is difficult to see the beauty of the soul with the eyes than the beauty of the body, in any case, some people are free by nature, and others are slaves, and it is both useful and just to be a slave to such people" ("Politics") [4, 38–52].

Due to the domination of Christianity in Europe in the Middle Ages, the problem of freedom was seen and solved within the framework of Christianity. In particular, Erasmus of Rotterdam stated that "free will is the naming of God. Therefore, the will of man is the grace of a very small god that flows freely from man. Man's will is his fantasy, his pride, which forces man to do evil; human nature is blind, he does not know his own power and, finally, because of his pride, he believes that he is capable of everything and knows everything" [5, 218-289].

The Renaissance period of the West re-understands its attitude to freedom. In particular, Pico della Mirandola believes that man is an extraordinary being with dignity, and says that he was given free will by God. This free will allows a person to create and change the reality that surrounds him. Every action of a person determines his place in the social hierarchy, a person acting on his will can reach a high level in social, political, as well as personal development, and his actions can bring him down to a very low position.

In the new era, the complex concept of freedom is approached in a new way. Freedom is seen as a law of nature, a law of human nature, a law of society. "The equality of a person with others, the right to be free in one's decisions and actions was announced, measures to ensure civil and political freedoms were developed" [6]. During this period, there is a departure from the laws of Christianity. Freedom becomes an inalienable right of every human being. However, the New Age philosophy takes the issues of freedom to a new level, related to aspects of freedom such as freedom of choice, freedom of action, responsibility, free will, limits of freedom, and the existence of absolute freedom.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The article uses the methods of comparative studies, analysis, synthesis, extrapolation, analogy, dialectical, synergetic, organismic methods of scientific knowledge.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

In the era of modernism, the forms of freedom "being free from something" and "being free for something" are distinguished, that is, positive freedom and negative freedom. These aspects are examined and revealed in detail in the philosophy of E. Fromm.

"Negative freedom is "being free from something", that is, the freedom that rejects attachment to the forces of nature and destroys it. In such conditions, a person faces a choice of new dependence, getting rid of this freedom through new subjugation, or rising to the level of positive freedom. Positive freedom is "being free for something", which allows the full realization of mental and emotional capacities, requires a person to realize them, because such freedom leads to the uniqueness and individuality of each person. is based on" [7].

In the philosophy of existentialism, freedom is understood and revealed as a great value, but it is noted that it also has the opposite side, such as being a burden and responsibility for a person, that a person is condemned to be free. "Being free is significantly more difficult than being a slave, a conformist, an indifferent flexible person. Therefore, not everyone tries to be really free, but everyone wants to appear free, to give the name of free, prefers the imitation of freedom, walks in the crowd, in order to impose personal responsibility on others. becomes q»[7]. In this regard, Karl Jaspers, representative of existentialism, said: "The main characteristic of our time is that, although everyone is thirsty for freedom, many people cannot stand it. They aspire to a place where they will be free from freedom for the sake of freedom," he writes [8, 53].

The problem of free will is also found in the philosophical works of Russian writers, who see freedom as the basis of human dignity and a burden burdened with responsibility.

An important aspect of understanding freedom is the relationship and interrelationship between freedom and rationality. Problems of a systematic approach to freedom A.N. Averyanov, I.V. Blauberg, E.G. Yudin, A.I. Uyomov, B.C. Tyukhtin, V.N. Sadovsky, V.P. Kuz'min, V.I. Volkova, A.A. Considered by a number of Russian scientists such as Denisov.

Also, the issues of personal freedom merge with the problem of the limits of this freedom: the problem of the space-time continuum arises. As a consequence of this, there are antinomies in human existence in relation to socio-cultural values, laws and issues of human freedom. "The situation in which modern man exists is such that he has answered the questions of what is good, what is evil, how a person should be, how he should relate to other people, and also provides a person with ready-made schemes that he can follow. the old norms of behavior that gave us "stopped working" now. Today, a person should search for a new meaning, new values and new ideals related to self-realization and self-determination in life»[9]. Therefore, the analysis of the problem of individual freedom in modern ontology is very important. The processes of social and cultural transformation taking place in Uzbekistan, the formation of a self-governing civil society and a legal state are able to interact with other people in the path of common goals, interests, and values in the society, as well

as It is possible only if there are free individuals who take the burden of personal responsibility for their actions.

Human aspects in a person are formed in the process of gaining more and more spiritual freedom, in which a person understands that freedom has its own reasonable limits, which are variable in the space-time continuum. In this regard, the Italian scientist A. Gramsci wrote in his work entitled "Art and Politics": "The standard of freedom is part of human understanding"[10].

Freedom is understood as the ability of a person to actively work in accordance with his interests and desires.

There are different degrees of freedom: natural freedom and positive nature of freedom. In this case, the realization of the natural rights of each person is limited by positive limits (legal, moral, value), which ensure that the other members of society have the same rights. The wider the possibilities of a person, the more significant the positive and negative consequences of his choice.

"Freedom is a social, mental and spiritual condition of a person. Freedom is inherently contradictory. On the one hand, freedom gives a person the opportunity to realize his potential, desires, on the other hand, it increases responsibility in a person [11, 85].

The versatility and variety of social relations determines the diversity of the manifestation of freedom, its various manifestations.

Moral freedom is a choice between good and evil, lower and higher. In the present era, a person indulges in his own desires and acts as a consumer. For example, we see a selfish consumer, a lazy consumer, a bad consumer, a consumer who is drowned in the mire of acquiring material goods and wealth. A selfish consumer satisfies his own needs at the expense of the freedom and interests of other people in order to achieve his selfish goals. Therefore, questions of freedom always have moral dimensions. This very aspect of freedom implies the purposeful denial of base desires, immorality, and selfishness by man.

Real freedom should have a hierarchy of axiological directions (landmarks) that do not allow to satisfy personal interests at the expense of society and others.

The concept of freedom is related to the concept of general goodness. For example, the moral essence of freedom is expressed in the service of high moral values. Morality allows a person to eliminate imperfection, improve his social and personal situation. It can be said that the existence of evil is a certain value for goodness, because only free action that negates evil acquires moral meaning.

Acting ethically means obeying morals and norms established by society, morality does not have the power to compel a person to obey out of fear, favor, or personal gain. Morality does not mean blind adherence to norms, but an attitude based on goodness. A person fulfills the requirements of morality precisely because moral behavior is worthy behavior. Thus, we see that morality and freedom not only require each other, but also serve as the basis of authenticity for each other.

Understanding freedom from an existential point of view is related to the moral dimension of freedom. In existentialism, first of all, a person's self-creation and responsibility for his actions constitute the substantial basis of freedom. In existentialism, freedom is a condition and method of self-realization. One of the representatives of French existentialism J.-P. Sartre believed that all people are free because consciousness cannot exclude freedom. According to his views, freedom is absolute, it exists in the form of action and activity. Unlimited freedom serves as the main thesis of the early works of the French thinker, in particular, the work "Existence and Absence" written in 1943[12]. In the works written in the later period, J.-P. Sartre distinguishes the aspects of freedom.

In existential philosophy, the important aspects of freedom are the choice of a goal by a person or freedom of will in it, as well as the ability to achieve a goal set by a person or the freedom of human actions. J.-P. believes that what distinguishes a person from other living beings is the ability to choose, to create oneself, to realize one's identity, to be responsible for one's choice. Sartre. Existential will forms the basis of every choice made by a person. A person determines his destiny by choosing.

German philosopher M. Heidegger explains human freedom differently. In particular, he says that the choice of a person implies the need to confront the last possibility of his existence, that is,

death, nothingness. "Due to his choice in the face of non-existence, man discovers what existence "says" to him both for himself and for the world" [13].

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"Religious existentialism shows that the human person is not a part of the world, but he is in relation to the world and God, and defines himself in relation to God. In the inner relationship with this God - meeting and communicating with him, a person gains strength for his free relationship with the world. It is God who is the guarantor of man's freedom against his subjugation by nature and society. This means that the human person is the absolute existential center, because he alone has the "feeler of pain and joy." Nothing else in the world of objects, according to them, has it»[13].

Freedom is a multifaceted concept and has direct political and economic aspects. Economic freedom refers to the relationship between the owners of the means of production and the labor force. Such unequal sharing is characteristic of many aspects of human existence, such as the transition from matriarchy to patriarchy and then to slavery. Economic freedom is related to free acceptance of economic decisions and actions.

Political freedom is directly related to human rights, they form the basis of the existence and development of a person with rights in society. Political freedom, which is a tool for the realization of other freedoms in the spiritual, epistemological, and economic spheres, is a special value of its own. An integral aspect of modern civilized human mentality is the need for political convenience that democracy provides. It is political freedom that reflects and guarantees spiritual freedom, that is, the free choice of worldview, religious belief, ideas and ideologies in general. In particular, when we talk about freedom of conscience, we refer to choosing any religious belief or not believing in religion at all (Article 31 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan). In this case, freedom reflects the social status of a person. However, from a political and legal point of view, freedom is a relative phenomenon, and it is manifested in a person's responsibility towards other people and the society in which he lives. These aspects form the basis of civil liberties.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS.

The level of freedom is always increasing, and at the same time, the progress of society is observed. A modern person has considerable freedom in determining the goals of his activity, because there are more than one real opportunities for development. People are free to choose the means to achieve their goals. Freedom, of course, is not absolute and is realized as the realization (turning into existence) of an opportunity by choosing a specific goal and plan.

It is known from the history of the development of the paradigms of civilizations that the establishment of freedom was accompanied by the struggle for personal, socio-economic and political rights of a person and against oppression, exploitation, discrimination and poor living conditions. Law is a form of social relations implemented by a person within the general norm. According to the philosophy of law, law is the rules of behavior that are mandatory for everyone, officially defined, accepted in an established order, guaranteed by the state, and regulating social relations. The legal form of freedom ensures formal equality and formal freedom of people in society.

Currently, four generations of human rights can be distinguished:

1. Liberal values (bourgeois revolutions in France, England, America). This generation of rights is related to civil and political rights, they reflect the obligation of the state to guarantee the personal rights of people, not to interfere in the sphere of personal freedom. Currently, this generation of rights is reinforced by international and national documents.

2. Socio-economic rights of Jesus (XIX century).

A system of rights to work, recreation, education, social security, medical care, etc. Ensuring and implementing this generation of rights determines the cultural development of human society. The distinctive features of these rights are that they are collective and can be exercised by the community.

3. Collective rights. This generation of rights is based on solidarity. Collective rights include development, peace and territorial integrity, independence, self-determination, awareness, freedom from oppression, rights to a clean ecological environment, and the common heritage of human civilization. This category of rights is reflected in both international and national documents.

4. Peace, nuclear security, space, environmental, information rights. This generation of rights began to form in the last decade of the 20th century. "F.M. According to Rudinsky, these rights should protect a person from threats related to experiments in the field of genetic inheritance, cloning and other discoveries in the field of biology" [15, 42].

Russian scientist A.B. Vengerov said: "The fourth generation is a legal response to the challenges of the 21st century, namely, the survival of humanity as a biological species, the preservation of civilization, and the further cosmic socialization of humanity. A new, fourth generation of rights is emerging, and, accordingly, international-legal procedural institutions that ensure these rights are emerging. International humanitarian law is being formed, worldly humanitarianism is taking place in the moral development of society»[16].

CONCLUSION.

Thus, it is expressed as a fundamental value, but it has its limits. The state should control the freedom of human rights not by means of violence and coercion, but by economic mechanism and strict observance of human rights. The state must guarantee the observance of human rights, recognizing that the value of the human being is higher than any value of the nation, class, group of people, etc.

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МАРКАЗИЙ ОСИЁ РЕНЕССАНСИ ЖУРНАЛИ

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ДАННЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ПОДГОТОВЛЕН К ИЗДАНИЮ В РАМКАХ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОГО НАУЧНОГО ПРОЕКТА ИЛ-4821891548
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В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УГРОЗ И ВЫЗОВОВ”

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